

Alpine plant trait combinations shape soil erosion dynamics and patterns

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Abstract

Soil erosion strongly affects high mountain slopes, such as deglaciating moraines, alpine grasslands and hiking trails. Plants can decrease soil erosion through adapted plant functional traits, such as high stem and leaf densities or dense root systems. However, due to trait trade-offs, a plant species cannot excel in all soil erosion reducing traits at once. Thus, to successfully protect and restore eroding mountain slopes, identification of common alpine trait combinations and quantification of their effects on soil erosion is needed. We used a semi-natural experiment in the Utrecht Botanic Gardens to test the effects of five different alpine plant species with contrasting trait combinations on soil erosion patterns and dynamics over two growing seasons. Our results show that trait combinations of relevant architectural, mechanical and life-history traits ranged from fast growth with high flexibility to slow, stiff and dense growth. We identified five different soil erosion plant strategies with contrasting effects developing over time. Two quickly growing species (“opportunist”, “conqueror”) swiftly reduced sediment yields (SYs) in the first year (up to 70%). Two more slowly growing species with stiff, dense stems (“blocker”, “builder”) significantly decreased SYs (up to 97%) in the second year, increased infiltration and built terraces. Adventitious roots and phenotypic plasticity additionally explain high soil stabilization effectiveness. A fifth species (“intensifier”) increased SYs by up to 250%. Using increasingly available trait data, more natural species with similar trait combinations and soil erosion strategies can now be identified. This will improve nature-based solutions on eroding hillslopes across mountain regions.

1 Introduction

Soil erosion by water, consisting of splash, inter-rill, rill and gully erosion processes, is an important geomorphic process not only limiting productivity of agricultural soils (Montgomery, 2007; Morgan, 2005; Poesen, 2018) but also affecting and degrading high mountain slopes (Gianinetto et al., 2020; Rapuc et al., 2024). Following glacier retreat, intensified soil erosion from moraine slopes provides loose sediments for more hazardous processes such as debris flows (Chiarle et al., 2007; Curry et al., 2006; Moore et al., 2009). Sediments transported into glaciofluvial systems can fill up glacier foreland reservoirs and limit their lifetime and efficiency (Bogen, 1988; Hauenstein, 2005; Ohler et al., 2023). On ski slopes, damaging of the upper soil layer and vegetation causes soil erosion, which in turn reduces soil quality and species diversity (Meijer zu Schlochtern et al., 2014; Piątek and Bernatek-Jakiel, 2024; Pohl et al., 2009). Similarly, soil erosion strongly affects recreational trails in mountain regions with high, unsustainable erosion rates (Bodoque et al., 2017; Salesa et al., 2019; Tarolli et al., 2013). Even small patch-wise soil erosion in alpine grasslands can have large cumulative effects on soil loss and land degradation (Alewell et al., 2015; Geitner et al., 2021; Mayr et al., 2019). Increasing rainfall intensities expected for high mountain regions (Hock et al., 2019) could disproportionately increase soil erosion in the future (Nearing et al. 2004, Poesen 2017).

Vegetation colonization and cover reduces soil erosion on mountain slopes (Eichel et al., 2016; Haselberger et al., 2021; Ohler et al., 2023). Plants' above-ground biomass protects the soil from splash erosion by raindrops and creates hydraulic roughness for water running down the slopes, thereby reducing flow velocity, increasing backwater depth and decreasing sediment transport (Morgan, 2005; Norris et al., 2008; Rey, 2003). Soil gets trapped in and around the

plants as flow velocities decrease, decreasing soil erosion not only on-site but also downslope ('off-site') (Erktan and Rey, 2013; Isselin-Nondedeu and Bédécarrats, 2007; Mekonnen et al., 2015). Above-ground biomass mainly matters for splash and inter-rill erosion, while for rill and gully erosion, roots become more important (Vannoppen et al., 2015). By increasing soil aggregate stability and water infiltration, as well as mechanically reinforcing soil by providing root cohesion, roots provide additional protection from soil erosion processes (De Baets et al., 2006; Gysels et al., 2005; Vannoppen et al., 2015).

Recent soil erosion research looked in more detail into the mechanisms by which plants actually influence soil erosion dynamics, finding that plant traits determining species' architecture, biomechanics and growth are highly important (Burylo et al., 2014; Kervroëdan et al., 2021). A plant trait is 'any morphological, physiological or phenological feature measurable at the individual level' (Violle et al., 2007, p. 889). Plant architecture, such as spatial distribution, area and density of stems and leaves, is important for increasing hydraulic roughness (De Baets et al., 2009; Kervroëdan et al., 2018) and trapping sediments (Burylo et al., 2012; Kervroëdan et al., 2018). For fixing the soil, fine, flexible roots, high root densities and root length density were identified as key traits (Burylo et al., 2012; De Baets et al., 2006).

Thus, to protect mountain soils from erosion and restore eroding mountain slopes, it would be desirable to employ plant species that have all these soil erosion-reducing 'effect' traits. However, finding a species with all effect traits at once is difficult (Burylo et al., 2014; De Baets et al., 2009). Plant species can usually only 'excel' in a few traits, as only few viable trait combinations exist (Diaz et al. 2016, Pierce et al. 2016). With limited available resources and stressful environmental constraints, species evolved to invest in certain plant parts, e.g. in

above-ground biomass or roots. This creates trait 'trade-offs' (Corenblit et al., 2024; Garland, 2014). In addition, before reducing soil erosion, plants first need to be able to establish on eroding mountain slopes ('establishment threshold', Eichel et al. 2016). This requires movement adapted 'response traits' such as clonal growth, flexible stems and resistance to burial and uprooting (Cannone and Gerdol, 2003; Eichel et al., 2023b; Kutschera et al., 1997; Schröter et al., 1926). Subsequently, species also need to be able to develop sufficient density or cover to become geomorphologically effective ('engineering threshold', Eichel et al. 2016), which depends on their 'effect traits' such as stem and leaf densities (Eichel et al., 2023a; Kervroëdan et al., 2019, 2018). Finally, for successful soil control, protection, restoration and management of eroded land using nature-based solutions, it is also desirable to find species that create long-term effects by facilitating vegetation succession (Burylo et al., 2014; De Baets et al., 2009; Stokes et al., 2014). On eroding mountain slopes, this was found to be well done by 'geomorphic ecosystem engineer' species which affect geomorphic processes to create habitats for themselves and other species (Eichel et al., 2023a; Miller and Lane, 2019).

Here we study how five common alpine plant species with contrasting above- and belowground trait combinations affect soil erosion processes. For this, we use semi-natural, outdoor soil erosion experiments, allowing us optimal accessibility and sufficient control on environmental factors in comparison to field experiments (cf. Ohler et al. 2023). By running the experiments over two years, we can evaluate effects of longer-term plant growth, adaptations and seasonal changes (cf. Kervroëdan et al., 2019).

Our objectives are to:

- (1) Assess key combinations of soil erosion effect and response traits for alpine plant species
- (2) Quantify effects of alpine plant species with different trait combinations on soil erosion patterns and dynamics
- (3) Link trait combinations and soil erosion effects to identify successful alpine soil erosion plant strategies for soil protection and restoration

2 Material and methods

Using semi-natural outdoor soil erosion experiments, we assessed the effects of trait combinations of five alpine plant species on soil erosion dynamics and patterns in Utrecht Botanic Gardens over two consecutive growing seasons. Prior to the experiment, we measured key response and effect traits of planted species and monitored their growth during and after the experiment. To quantify soil erosion dynamics and pattern evolution over time, we used weekly runoff experiments, natural rainfall, as well as structure-from-motion approaches.

2.1 Experimental setup in Utrecht Botanic Gardens

We conducted our soil erosion experiments from 12-6-23 to 23-9-24 on the soil-mantled slope of a historic fort in the Utrecht Botanic Gardens (Netherlands). Mean annual air temperatures in De Bilt, 2.5 km from the botanic gardens, were 11.77 °C in 2023, with 1180 mm of rainfall and around 1840 hours of sunshine (KNMI, 2023). On the slope, we set up six plywood boxes, each 2.40 m long and 0.65 m wide, arranged to a slope gradient of 9.3° (Figure 1). While the plots were partly overshadowed by trees, installed rainfall collectors (Figure 1) found no significant difference in weekly rainfall sums between the plots (Figure S1). Each box

contained a soil filled area with a size of 1.5×0.6×0.3 m. To enable our alpine plants to successfully grow, we used a mixture of 20% fine grit (mean grain size 6.9 mm) and 80% natural soil consisting of 73.31% sand, 0.5% clay and 26.19% silt. Upslope from the soil-filled area, we placed a rough-textured concrete tile to diffuse incoming artificial runoff during the experiment. Each plot ended in a custom-made plastic funnel (Fig. 1d) to direct water and eroded sediments into plastic containers for weighing and laboratory analyses.

To test effects of different trait combinations on soil erosion, we selected alpine species with contrasting life forms and associated trait combinations. All species not only grow on eroding or unstable slopes (Al Hayek et al., 2014; Eichel et al., 2023a) but are also able to grow under the garden's climatic conditions (Figure 1): *Campanula cochleariifolia* Lam., *Dryas octopetala* L., *Festuca gautieri* (Hack.) K.Richt., *Muehlenbeckia axillaris* (Hook.f.Endl.) and *Larix decidua* Mill. *C. cochleariifolia* is a perennial, clonally reproducing pioneer species growing from stout taproots with creeping stems and round, basal leaves in rosettes on moving sediments from the Pyrenees to the Carpathians and Northern Balkan Peninsula (Govaerts, 2024; Lauber and Wagner, 2018; Schröter et al., 1926). *D. octopetala* is a prostrate shrub with a circumpolar distribution, forming dense, several meter-wide mats on unstable slopes through stout prostrate stems and numerous leaves (Eichel et al., 2023a; Elkington, 1971). *F. gautieri* is a dwarf grass species growing in circular to elliptic cushions on steep, calcareous scree slopes in European mountain ranges from Morocco to Romania (Al Hayek et al., 2014; Govaerts, 2024). *M. axillaris* (Hook.f.Endl.) is a prostrate or straggling shrub with small, round leaves and creeping or underground stems and branches, forming stable patches on moving debris in New Zealand and Australia (Al Hayek et al., 2014). *L. decidua* is a light demanding, deciduous tree species with one upright stem, outgoing branches and flexible needles in bunches of 20-40, growing on disturbed ground in the Alps, Sudeten Mountains and Carpathians (da Ronch

et al., 2016; Govaerts, 2024; Lauber and Wagner, 2018). For all species except *F. gautieri*, response traits to survive slope movements have been reported, including clonal growth (*C. cochleariifolia*, *D. octopetala*), burial tolerance (*C. cochleariifolia*, *D. octopetala*, *M. axillaris*, *L. decidua*) and resprouting capacity (*D. octopetala*, *M. axillaris*, *L. decidua*) (Eichel et al., 2023a; Kattge et al., 2020; Klimešová and Bello, 2009). Prior to planting, we measured further response, as well as effect traits for each species (see section 2.3).

We planted one alpine plant species per plot at the lower 60x50 cm of the soil filled areas on 28-2-23. Per species, we planted sufficient individuals to create about 10% vegetation cover (Figure 1). This enabled all plots to sufficient vegetation cover (>15-45%) to become effective in soil erosion reduction (Haselberger et al., 2021; Moreno-de las Heras et al., 2009). One plot remained bare as control plot against which we compared soil erosion measurements from vegetated plots. We added a seventh set of small horizontal boxes as a control for vegetation growth with an explanatory information sign for the public. *L. decidua* was leafless during planting but quickly developed leaves in the weeks prior to starting the experiment. The plants were given several weeks to establish before the start of a first test phase of the experiments end of April 2023. As plant cover quickly differed between the species, we added additional individuals on 15-5-23 (Figure 1) to ensure similar cover values, and related effects on soil erosion dynamics, for all species. During dry periods, we watered the plants in the plots every two to three days, using the same amount of water for each plot and taking care not to create runoff and erosion while watering.

Figure 1: Soil erosion experimental setup in Utrecht Botanic Gardens (Netherlands). (a) Sketch of setup showing planting of boxes, location of rainfall collectors and ground control points. Numbers behind species' names give plant cover (%) at time of planting. (b) Photo of soil erosion experiment at start in June 2023 (control vegetation plot is to the left).

Our experiment was conducted over two growing seasons and covered several soil erosion processes: inter-rill erosion and rill erosion created in a weekly runoff experiment, and splash erosion due to naturally occurring rainfall between runoff events. For the runoff experiment, we subjected each plot each week to 13 l artificial runoff, representing a typical monthly rainfall event (14.3 mm/day) on an alpine moraine slope in Switzerland (MeteoSwiss, 2022). Due to varying water pressure in the botanic garden's water reservoir, discharge from our

garden hose varied between 0.26 and 0.39 l/s. To create sheet flow, water ran from the hose over the concrete tiles through a custom-made plastic device (Videos S1-S6). Once the water reached the funnel, we added red food dye as a tracer to assess flow velocity (m/s) in videos taken with an iPad Pro 11". After each runoff experiment, filled plastic containers were weighed and put into a shed for two days to let suspended sediments settle. Subsequently, we drained the water and removed the sediments to let them dry for at least 48 h at 105°C (longer if needed). From their dry weight we derived runoff sediment yields (runoff SY; g m⁻²) for each artificial runoff event. By subtracting sediment dry weights and box weight from weight of the filled boxes, we estimated infiltration in liters per runoff event. Between artificial runoff events, we captured sediment eroded by rainfall in the boxes and derived weekly rainfall sediment yields (rainfall SY, g m⁻²) in a similar way. We paused our measurements outside of the growing season (27-9-23 – 12-5-24). Before restarting on 13-5-24, we refilled the eroded depressions formed in winter in the upper 50 cm of each plot with sediment. At the bare plot, the concrete tile was unfortunately leaking from 07.08.23-26.09.23, so all data except SY (rainfall) had to be excluded from further analysis. We also excluded values for the bare plot on 08.07.24 and for *C. cochleariifolia* and *F. gautieri* on 05.08.24 due to further leakages. For *M. axillaris*, it was mostly impossible to determine flow velocities from 27.05.24 onwards due to dense growth on the funnel. After completion of the experiments, we discovered in our videos that for *C. cochleariifolia*, *D. octopetala* and *L. decidua* water leaked slightly between the funnel and the box. We estimate water loss at a maximum of 100 ml per runoff event, making presented sediment yields runoff minimum and infiltration maximum values.

2.3 Plant trait measurements and identification of species' trait combinations

Prior to the experiment (10-3-23), we measured plant traits for three individuals per species, from the same batch as the planted individuals, using standard methods (Freschet et al., 2021; Pérez-Harguindeguy et al., 2013). We selected traits that were shown to be relevant for affecting runoff, soil erosion and slope stability ('effect traits', cf. Burylo et al., 2014; De Baets et al., 2009; Kervroëdan et al., 2021), as well as leaf traits indicative of plant response to disturbance ('response traits'; Table 1; Pierce et al., 2017, 2013). For each individual, we measured its length, width and vegetative height and counted (i) total number of stems, (ii) branches and (iii) leaves. From this we calculated total interception volume and stems per cm² (Table 1). For five stems and branches per individual, we measured stem and branch lengths (LS) as well as diameters (D) using a caliper. From this, we calculated mean (projected) and total stem and branch areas ($LS \times D$). Subsequently, we separated above- from below-ground biomass and weighed it per individual to assess initial biomass planted per plot (mean biomass of measured individuals \times number of individuals planted). We then sampled a several cm long piece of stem from each individual, determined its volume ($V = (0.5D)^2 \times \pi \times LS$) and then oven-dried the section at 70° C for 72 hours to derive stem specific density (SSD) (Table 1; Pérez-Harguindeguy et al. 2013). To analyze leaf response traits, we sampled five leaves per individual and determined leaf area (LA), specific leaf area (SLA) and leaf dry matter content (LDMC) using standard procedures involving image analysis (ImageJ 1.53k), weighing, drying (70° for 72 hours) and re-weighing dried leaves using high-precision scales. Per individual, we calculated mean leaf areas to derive its total leaf area and leaf density (see Table 1). For *L. decidua*, still leafless in March, we sampled leaves of the two planted individuals on 22.05.2023 and analyzed them as detailed above. For measuring root traits, we cut off roots of each individual, rinsed and weighed them to determine below-ground biomass. We then

calculated root density (RD) by dividing total root biomass by the volume of the plastic containers in which the species were delivered. To determine root area ratios (RAR), we counted the number of roots in nine diameter (D) classes (<0.25 mm, < 0.5 mm, <0.75 mm, <1 mm, < 1.5 mm, < 2 mm, < 3 mm, < 4 mm, <5 mm) and calculated root area per diameter class ($Ar = (\pi / 4) \times D^2$). Subsequently, we calculated RARs as the sum of root areas from all diameter classes, divided by the total rooted area (width \times length of plastic containers) (cf. De Baets et al., 2006).

Once the experiment was finished, we assessed invested biomass during the experiments per species. For this, we sampled the above-ground biomass of three individuals per plot and took root samples or three individuals using 20 cm deep cores with a 20 cm diameter. We additionally noted presence of adventitious roots, as well as ramets as indicators for clonal growth. From the samples, we determined weight of above-ground biomass per individual and, after careful washing, weight of the total below-ground biomass in the core. Subsequently, we calculated final biomass (above- and below-ground) per plot by multiplying mean biomass from the three sampled individuals with the number of planted individuals. We also calculated root-shoot ratios per plot by dividing invested above-ground by invested below-ground biomass to assess in where species' focused their investments.

To identify combinations of key soil erosion effect and response traits for each species, we used a principal component analysis (PCA) for our pre-experiment trait dataset (Table 1). Prior to PCA, we standardized our data using a zero-mean approach. As *L. decidua* was leafless during pre-experiment measurements and therefore missed key effect traits, it could not be included into the PCA. Instead, we used boxplots to assess key response and effect traits for *L. decidua* in comparison to the other species.

Table 1: Overview of soil erosion related effect and response traits measured on three individuals per species prior to the experiments.

Trait	Unit	Definition	Reference
<i>Effect traits</i>			
Leaf density	cm ² /cm ³	Total leaf area per total interception volume	Burylo et al., (2012)
Root Area Ratio (RAR)	cm ² /cm ² (-)	Total root cross sectional area per rooted area of soil	De Baets et al., (2006)
Root density (RD)	kg m ³	Mass of living plant roots per soil volume	Freschet et al., (2021); Vannoppen et al., (2015)
Stem-specific density (SSD)	mg mm ⁻³	Oven dry mass of stem section per stem section volume	Pérez-Harguindeguy et al., (2013)
Stems per cm ²	Stems cm ⁻²	Number of stems per area (L x W) of individual	Kervroëdan et al., (2019)
Total branch area	cm ²	Number of branches × mean branch area per individual	Kervroëdan et al., (2018)
Total interception volume	cm ³	Individual length × width × vegetative height	Burylo et al., (2012)
Total leaf area	cm ²	Number of leaves × mean leaf area per individual	Kervroëdan et al., (2019)
Total stem area	cm ²	Number of stems × mean stem area per individual (Kervroëdan et al., (2018)
<i>Response traits</i>			

Specific leaf area (SLA)	mm ² mg ⁻¹	Leaf area divided by oven-dry mass	Pérez-Harguindeguy et al., (2013)
Leaf dry matter content (LDMC)	mg g ⁻¹	Oven dry leaf mass divided by fresh leaf mass	Pérez-Harguindeguy et al., (2013)

2.5 Assessing species' effects soil erosion dynamics

To assess effects of each species on soil erosion dynamics, we used boxplots showing (i) sediment yield (SY) runoff, (ii) SY rainfall, (iii) flow velocity and (iv) infiltration per species. To test whether effects of species on soil erosion dynamics were significantly different, we performed analyses of variance (ANOVA). Prior to analysis, we tested if variables meet ANOVA assumptions of normality using a Shapiro-Wilk normality test and transformed them using a square-root transformation if necessary. Following ANOVA, we did Tukey honestly significant difference (HSD) tests for significance of differences between individual groups. For variables not meeting ANOVA assumptions (SY rainfall), we did a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test, following a post-hoc pairwise Wilcoxon test with adjusted p-values according to Benjamini and Hochberg (1995) to test for significant differences between individual groups.

To quantify reduction in soil erosion per species and in relation to invested biomass, we first also calculated the reduction in eroded sediment for each species by subtracting eroded sediment per vegetated plot from eroded sediment from the bare plot. We did this for the total sum of eroded sediments (g) for both runoff and rainfall, as well as per year, calculating the percentage of reduction (%) for each year and process (runoff, rainfall). By subtracting initial biomass per plot from final biomass, we estimate invested biomass (above- and below-

ground) per species. Subsequently, we calculated reduction in eroded sediment in comparison to the bare plot (g) per g of invested biomass (above- and below-ground) for each species.

All statistical analyses were conducted using RStudio (version 2022.02.1), using the 'stats' package for PCA (prcomp), Shapiro-Wilk normality test (shapiro.test), ANOVA (aov), Tukey tests (TukeyHSD), Kruskal-Wallis test (Kruskal.test) and pairwise Wilcoxon test (pairwise.wilcox.test, with adjusted p method). PCA plot and boxplots were created using the 'ggplot2' package.

2.4 Assessing species' effects on soil erosion patterns

To map soil erosion patterns and vegetation growth, we used a structure from motion (SfM) approach (cf. Eltner et al., 2015; Hänsel et al., 2016). With a GoPro camera (wide angle setting, 1 s time lapse), we mimicked a drone flight with a lawn mower pattern, with distances of 50 cm between the flight paths to create sufficient overlap. For referencing, we placed 18 ground control points (GCPs) on fixed wooden stakes at the side of each container, as well as two additional GCPs per plot on their wooden walls separating the plots (Figure 1). At the end of the experiments in October 2024, we took an additional set of SfM images after all above-ground biomass was carefully removed from the plots to assess sediment trapping in the plants.

To derive weekly digital surface models and orthophotos of the experiment, SfM images were processed in Agisoft Metashape (version 2.1.0). To account for potential variations in lens parameters over time, separate camera groups were created for each time series. Initially, all datasets were co-aligned following the methodology outlined in Nota et al. (2022). Subsequently, inaccurate points were removed using the gradual selection tool to refine the

sparse point cloud. The resulting sparse point clouds were then scaled using ground control points (GCPs; see Figure 1). The distances between the GCPs were measured and incorporated as scale bars in Agisoft Metashape to ensure accurate real-world dimensions of the analyzed objects. For each box, a total of eight ground control points were utilized. Following scaling, a dense point cloud was generated, and points with low confidence were filtered out to improve the accuracy of the final result. The processed dense point cloud was then employed to generate both a digital elevation model (DEM) and an orthomosaic for each time series.

To assess soil erosion and deposition patterns within the plots over the two experimental seasons (2023, 2024), we calculated DEMs of Difference (DoDs) between selected DEMs for season 2023 (12-6-23 – 26-9-23) and 2024 (15-6-24 – 23-9-24) in QGIS (version 3.36, Maidenhead). Subsequently, we calculated minimum levels of detection for each compared dataset with a 95% confidence interval, using in total 40 stable points distributed along the box frames (Williams, 2012). By manually delineating species' individuals in the orthophotos at the beginning and end of each experimental season, we were able to track their growth during the experiment.

Several smaller problems occurred in our longer-term experimental setup, including leaking water and developing moss cover. Based on our estimates, water leaking from the *C. cochleariifolia*, *D. octopetala* and *L. decidua* plots made up less than 1% of water added to the plot, with consistent contrast in SYs, flow velocities and infiltration between the plots despite similar leakage. Therefore, we consider our results still interpretable, keeping in mind that presented flow velocities and SYs are minimum values, while presented infiltration values are maximum values. Developing moss cover in all plots in 2024 could not be removed without strong disturbance of the plots. Moss cover is known to effectively reduce soil erosion shown

(Gall et al., 2024; García-Carmona et al., 2020). However, in our experiment, effects of moss cover do not reflect in SYs, with lowest SY for plots with lowest moss cover (*M. axillaris*, *D. octopetala*), and high SYs for plots with highest cover (*C. cochleariifolia*, bare) (Figures 3a,b; 4). Thus, despite some limitations in our data, partly unavoidable for semi-natural experiments run over a longer time, we believe key effects of alpine plant species on soil erosion dynamics remain well interpretable.

3 Results

3.1 Combinations of key effect and response traits of investigated alpine plant species

Principal component analysis of response and effect traits measured before the experiment explained 63.75% of variance in its first two components, which together show key combinations of effect and response traits per species (Figure 2a). The main gradient in trait variation (PC1, 39.59%) was explained by high leaf density, total branch area and SLA characterizing *M. axillaris* towards the negative direction, versus high number of stems per cm², LDMC and leaf density characterizing *D. octopetala* towards the positive direction. The second gradient (PC2, 24.16%) was explained by high total stem area, root density and SSD characterizing *F. gautieri* in the upper part, versus high RAR and number of branches per cm² characterizing *C. cochleariifolia* in the lower part. *L. decidua* stood out from the other species by its high total stem area, root density and SLA, but low SSD and LDMC (Fig. 2 b-f). At the end of the experiment, we observed very high numbers of adventitious roots for *M. axillaris* (>100 per individual) and high numbers for *D. octopetala* (mean 75 per individuum), but low numbers (< 10 per individuum) for *F. gautieri* and *C. cochleariifolia* (Table 2). While *D. octopetala* and *F. gautieri* did not reproduce clonally during the experiment, *C. cochleariifolia* developed nine ramets and *M. axillaris* one ramet. Overall, *M. axillaris* invested most above-

and below-ground biomass during the experiment, followed by *F. gautieri* and *D. octopetala*. *C. cochleariifolia* invested considerably less into above-ground biomass, but comparably much more into its below-ground biomass, resulting in a root-shoot ratio of nearly 1:1, with ratios of 1:3-1:5 for the other species. For *L. decida*, biomass could not be assessed as both individuals died off in the second year due to repeated grazing by rabbits.

Table 2: Development of alpine species' during the experiment, including number of developed adventitious roots per individual (estimate), ramets per plot and invested above (AGB) and below-ground (BGB) biomass, including its root-shoot ratios.

	Adventitious roots	Developed ramets	Invested AGB	Invested BGB	Root-shoot ratio
<i>C. cochleariifolia</i>	<10	9	121.44	103.75	0.85
<i>F. gautieri</i>	<10	0	780.05	264.63	0.34
<i>D. octopetala</i>	>75	0	739.89	170.65	0.23
<i>M. axillaris</i>	>100	1	1326.49	290.29	0.22
<i>L. decida</i>	0	0	NA	NA	NA

Figure 1: Investigated alpine plant species differ in their key response and effect traits towards soil erosion. (a) Principal component analysis (PCA) showing key effect and response traits for four species (*C. cochlearifolia*, *D. octopetala*, *F. gautieri*, *M. axillaris*) in four clusters. PC1 explains 39.59% of the variance, PC2 explains a further 24.16% of the variance. (b-f) Boxplots of selected stem, branch, root and leaf traits showing key traits for *Larix decidua* (5) in comparison to the other four species (1: *C. cochlearifolia*, 2: *D. octopetala*, 3: *F. gautieri*, 4: *M. axillaris*).

3.2 Plant species' influences on soil erosion dynamics: sediment yields, flow velocities and infiltration

Our results show several significant differences between runoff sediment yields, rainfall sediment yields, flow velocities and infiltration both between plots with different species, and between vegetated plots and the bare control plot (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Boxplots showing clear differences in species' effects on soil erosion dynamics and their changes between 2023 (left boxes per species) and 2024 (right boxes). ANOVA and Kruskal-Wallis results indicate significant ($p < 0.05$) differences between species groups, except for SY (runoff) in 2023. Different letters indicate

significant differences between different species per year (Tukey's HSD test or pairwise Wilcoxon test, $\alpha = 0.05$). (a) Runoff sediment yield ($\text{g}/\text{m}^2/\text{event}$). (b) Rainfall sediment yield ($\text{g}/\text{m}^2/\text{week}$). (c) Flow velocity (m/s). (d) Infiltration (l).

For runoff erosion, SYs differed between species in 2023 (Figure 3a), with lowest SY for *M. axillaris* and second lowest for *C. cochleariifolia* in 2023, and highest values for the bare plot, *L. decidua* and *D. octopetala*. Differences between groups however were not significant (ANOVA: $F=2.03$, $p > 0.05$). In 2024, runoff SYs overall decreased, with significant differences between species (ANOVA: $F=20.82$, $p < 0.001$). *F. gautieri*, *D. octopetala* and *M. axillaris* had significantly lower SYs than the bare control plot and the *L. decidua* plot, for which the SY was even significantly higher than for the bare plot. For *C. cochleariifolia*, SY was significantly lower than from the *L. decidua*, but not than for the bare plot.

For rainfall erosion, sediment yields were generally much lower in 2023 than runoff sediment yields. Clear, significant differences in rainfall sediment yields existed between plots for both 2023 (Kruskal-Wallis: $H=18.00$, $p < 0.001$) and 2024 (Kruskal-Wallis: $H=22.09$, $p < 0.001$). In 2023, rainfall sediment yield was highest for the bare control plot, with significantly lower values for *C. cochleariifolia* and *M. axillaris*. For *D. octopetala*, *F. gautieri* and *L. decidua*, SYs did not significantly differ from the other plots. In 2024, rainfall SYs overall dropped, with a significantly lower SY for *D. octopetala* than for *L. decidua* and the bare plot. For *C. cochleariifolia*, *F. gautieri* and *M. axillaris*, significantly less sediment eroded than for *L. decidua* but not significantly less than for the bare plot.

Flow velocities overall dropped from 2023 to 2024, except for *L. decidua*, and significantly differed between plots in both 2023 (ANOVA: $F=5.80$, $p < 0.001$) and 2024 (ANOVA: $F=40.66$, $p < 0.001$). In 2023, flow velocities for *L. decidua* were in a similar range as for the bare plot, while flow velocities were significantly lower for *D. octopetala* and *M. axillaris* than for *L. decidua* but not the bare plot. Excluding *L. decidua*, flow velocities were highest for *F. gautieri*,

though not significantly higher than for the other species. In 2024, flow velocities were significantly lowest for *M. axillaris* and second lowest for *D. octopetala* and *F. gautieri*. Flow velocities for *C. cochleariifolia* were significantly higher than for those three species, with no significant difference to flow velocities in the bare plot. For *L. decidua*, flow velocities were significantly higher than in any other plot, including the bare plot.

Infiltration significantly differed between the plots in both 2023 (ANOVA: $F=8.28$, $p < 0.001$) and 2024 (ANOVA: $F=8.38$, $p < 0.001$), with significantly lower infiltration values for both *L. decidua* and the bare plot in both years. Infiltration was highest for *C. cochleariifolia* in 2023, though not significantly different from *F. gautieri*, *D. octopetala* and *M. axillaris*. While infiltration did not change for *C. cochleariifolia* in 2024, infiltration strongly increased for the other three species.

3.3 Reductions in eroded sediments in relation to soil erosion processes and invested biomass

Soil erosion was reduced by all plants more strongly for rainfall than for runoff (Table 3). For runoff, *M. axillaris* kept most sediment in place with more than 500 g less eroded than from the bare plot. In contrast, *D. octopetala* had little effect and *L. decidua* even increased erosion, releasing over 700 g more than the bare plot during the experiment. Reduction in runoff and rainfall erosion furthermore differed between the years, with different species showing different trends. Both *C. cochleariifolia* and *M. axillaris* reduced runoff erosion less in 2024 than in 2023, while *D. octopetala* showed a very strong increase in erosion reduction from 12% higher erosion than the control plot in 2023 to 40% less erosion than the control plot in 2024. *M. axillaris* reduced erosion most strongly in 2023, but overall its effect on runoff erosion decreased by 25% over the years. Erosion for *L. decidua* was already slightly higher than the bare plot in 2023 and was more than 250% higher in 2024. Eroded sediments

included large quantities of coarse grit that could be heard dropping into the bucket during the runoff experiment (Video S6). For rainfall, overall reduction in erosion was much higher than for runoff, especially for *D. octopetala*, with all species increasing their reducing effect in 2024 except for *L. decidua*, which increased rainfall erosion in 2024 by 20% in comparison to the bare plot. The biomass that the species invested to reduce soil erosion (Table 3) stands out for *M. axillaris* by its high investment in above-ground biomass (more than 1.3 kg), while *C. cochleariifolia* invested the least biomass (121 g above, 103 g below), with a rather similar investment in both above and below-ground biomass (root-shoot ratio 0.85). Both prostrate shrubs *D. octopetala* and *M. axillaris* invested much less in below-ground biomass (root-shoot ratios 0.22-0.23), reflecting in their low RARs and root densities (Figure 2). With its low investment in biomass but good reduction in eroded sediment, *C. cochleariifolia* created by far the most reduction in runoff soil erosion per invested biomass (about 0.35 g reduction per invested biomass). *M. axillaris* also showed a good reduction per invested biomass, especially for invested below-ground biomass (0.22 g reduction per g biomass). In contrast, for *D. octopetala* runoff erosion actually slightly increased per invested g biomass for both above- and below-ground biomass. For rainfall erosion, however, *D. octopetala* was most effective in reducing per invested below-ground biomass (0.23 g reduction per g biomass), while it was second most effective per invested above-ground biomass (0.06 g). Only *C. cochleariifolia* was more effective (0.13 g). *M. axillaris* and *F. gautieri* were similarly effective per g invested above (reduction 0.03-0.04 g) and below-ground biomass (reduction 0.11-0.14 g).

Table 3: Total reduction in in eroded sediment for runoff and rainfall erosion per species in comparison to the bare control plot in g as indicator for species' erosion reducing potential. Furthermore, reduction in erosion in comparison to the bare plot in % is shown for 2023 and 2024, as well as reduced erosion (runoff, rainfall) in relation to invested above- (ABG) and below-ground biomass (BGB; cf. Table 2). For 2023, only runoff erosion measurements until 07.08.2023 are included, as afterwards, the concrete tile of the bare plot was broken and could only be replaced in 2024 to not disturb the experiment. For *L. decidua*, no biomass-related data is available as both individuals died mid-2024.

Species	Total reduction runoff erosion (g)	Total reduction rainfall erosion (g)	Reduction runoff erosion 2023 (%)	Reduction runoff erosion 2024 (%)	Reduction rainfall erosion 2023 (%)	Reduction rainfall erosion 2024 (%)	Reduced erosion AGB (g/g)	Reduced erosion AGB (g/g)	Reduced erosion BGB(g/g)	Reduced erosion BGB (g/g)
<i>Campanula</i>										
<i>cochleariifolia</i>	313,78	826,45	40,02	15,35	77,02	88,46	0,33	0,13	0,39	0,15
<i>Festuca</i>										
<i>gautieri</i>	172,18	766,97	12,75	29,65	62,83	88,94	0,02	0,04	0,05	0,11
<i>Dryas</i>										
<i>octopetala</i>	37,21	779,54	12,13	40,71	59,16	94,1	-0,06	0,06	-0,07	0,24

Muehlenbeckia

<i>axillaris</i>	557,69	863,3	65,43	40,41	74,34	97,24	0,05	0,03	0,23	0,14
<i>Larix decidua</i>	-780,5	-20,91	-4,05	-258,3	21,3	-20,62	NA	NA	NA	NA

3.2 Spatial erosion and deposition patterns and species' growth over time

Terrain and orthophoto analysis in combination with close-up photography show clear species-specific spatial erosion and deposition patterns linked to species' growth patterns (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Spatial soil erosion (orange), deposition (blue) and vegetation growth patterns in 2023 and 2024 for each plot, combined with close-up photography of observed erosion and deposition at individual plants.

Orthophoto 2023 from 26.09.23, 2024 from 02.10.24 (removed above-ground biomass). Plant outlines, if possible per individual, show individual plants at beginning and end of measurements each year (see dates on left). For 2024, the DEM of Difference was calculated between start of experiment and removal of biomass beginning of October, showing removed biomass in orange. (a) *C. cochleariifolia*. Trapping of sediments, burial of stems and ramets (in back) becoming independent was observed (23.05.23) (b) *F. gautieri*. Dry patches downstream after runoff, indicating beginning channelization effects, with a deep channel visible at plot sides, were observed (19.06.23). (c) *D. octopetala*. Observed trapping of coarse sediment behind stems of dense, stiff *Dryas* seedlings (25.04.23). (d) *M. axillaris*. Fine sediment accumulation at the back of *Muehlenbeckia*'s buried stems was observed (02.06.23). (e) *L. decidua*. Beginning of channel development between thick single stems observed on 26.06.23. Level of detection 0.005 m (transparent color).

In the first year, *C. cochleariifolia* showed erosion upstream and around the plants, as well as deposition of fines in the individual patches, which extended by clonal growth with many ramets (Figure 5e). *C. cochleariifolia* individuals grew quickly and considerably in the first experiment season, with all individuals overlapping with a least one other at the end of the season (Figure 5 a, b). During runoff, some stems slightly moved in the flow (Video S1, 27-05-24). In the second year, *C. cochleariifolia* started with a similar plant cover as in 2023 and did not reach higher cover values. After removal of above-ground biomass, sediment deposition both within and around the plant individuals could be observed with no clear spatial pattern. In the first year, *F. gautieri* showed clear erosion around established individuals, which grew in a predominantly round shape, expanded only slowly laterally and did not join at the end of the experimental period in 2023 (Figure 4b). Observations showed dry patches in the lee of the individuals (Figure 4b) indicating flow diversion around the patches, consistent with observed channels at the plot sides. At the beginning of the second year, all *F. gautieri* individuals were already joined. Erosion is visible at the lower, uncovered plot parts right and left of the individuals, while a clear band of deposited sediments shows upstream of the

tussocks, with runoff videos showing a strong upstream backwater effect (several cm) (Video S2, 09-09-24). For *D. octopetala*, terrain elevation did not change 50 cm upstream of the patch in the first year, indicating that either no erosion or deposition happened or they matched in volume (Figure 4c). *D. octopetala*'s individuals grew most slowly at the beginning due to drought stress, two individuals died off in June 2023. All individuals initially had a round shape. However, two individuals in the upper row, regularly affected by soil erosion, grew over time to elongated shapes mostly oriented perpendicular to the flow. All individuals had a joint edge with at least one other at the end of the experimental period in 2023. Around the individuals, some erosion is visible. Trapping of coarse and fine sediments could be well observed already behind small *Dryas* seedlings at the beginning of the experiment (Figure 4c). In the second year, *D. octopetala* completely covered the lower part of the plots. Again, little terrain change occurred upstream of the vegetated area, with a clear, band-like sediment deposition occurring upstream from the 2024 initial plant outlines, forming a distinct small terrace. Like for *F. gautieri*, runoff videos show a backwater effect, though less pronounced (Video S3, 16-09-24). Similar to *D. octopetala*, no terrain change was apparent for about 50 cm upstream of *M. axillaris* individuals in 2023 (Figure 4d). *M. axillaris* individuals were already joined at the beginning of the experimental period and quickly covered the lower part of the plot in the first month, expanding up to 1 m upstream by individual prostrate or underground stems until the end of the experimental period in 2023. We observed considerable accumulation of fine sediments upstream of the individuals during the experimental run-in period, burying its stems (Figure 5h). In the second year, *M. axillaris* covered about 75% of the plot, with individual stems reaching up to the tile. Erosion was only detectable in the uncovered part, with clear deposition showing upstream from its plant outline at the beginning of the 2024 experimental season, though a backwater effect was not visible in the flow (Video S4, 16-09-

24). Finally, *L. decidua* showed erosion within the entire plot in 2023 (Figure 4e), except below the two individuals where terrain changes could not be assessed with our SfM approach. Total *L. decidua* cover barely changed in 2023, with differences in *L. decidua* shape resulting from errors in the orthophotos. We observed the development of a small channel between the two *Larix* individuals, also shown by the tracer in runoff videos at the end of the first experimental season (Video S5, 04.09.23). In 2024, *L. decidua* individuals were repeatedly grazed by rabbits, causing them to die off in mid-2024 with their stems, branches and root systems remaining in place. Erosion only occurred in the lower two thirds of the plot, however, runoff videos show strong channelization (Video S6, 16.09.24). For the bare plot, erosion was dominant in both years, with decreasing extent in the second year and concentration in the upper third. Erosion shows no spatial patterns except limited erosion in 2024 where a moss cover developed. Runoff videos show little flow concentration even at the end of the experiment (Video S7, 16-09-24). Moss cover also developed on all other plots, with highest final cover for *C. cochleariifolia* and lowest for *M. axillaris* and *D. octopetala* (Figure 5).

4 Discussion

4.1 Key response and effect trait combinations of selected alpine species

We found that two main gradients in response and effect traits characterize our alpine species (Figure 2), both in relation to quick growth or stress tolerance (main gradient NMDS1), and in relation to flow resistance and soil stabilization (second gradient NMDS2). Our main gradient in species' traits matches the leaf economics spectrum (Pérez-Harguindeguy et al., 2013; Pierce et al., 2013; Wright et al., 2004), ranging from quick growth (high SLA) with high total leaf and branch areas to slow growth (low SLA) with high physical leaf resistance (high LDMC), clustered stems and leaves (NMDS1, Figure 2). A second gradient (NMDS2) separates our

species into species with clustered, rigid stems (high SSD and total stem area), creating high flow resistance, versus species with flexible stems (low SSD) bending in the flow (cf. Corenblit et al., 2024; Diehl et al., 2017; Pérez-Harguindeguy et al., 2013). Furthermore, our second gradient relates to different soil stabilization strategies with dense, heavy roots (high root density) decreasing soil detachment (cf. Vannoppen et al., 2015) versus high root areas increasing soil cohesion (cf. De Baets et al., 2006). Within the two gradients, each alpine species is characterized by a specific trait combination (Figure 2, Figure 5a). *L. decidua* possesses highest above and below-ground biomass with short-lived, flexible leaves (high SLA). A single, thick but flexible stem (high stem area, low SSD) with numerous branches makes it resilient to slope processes, e.g. snow avalanching (da Ronch et al., 2016). Its heavy, deep rooting taproot system (high root density) offers good resistance to pulling forces (da Ronch et al., 2016). *C. cochleariifolia*'s creeping stems are flexible (high SSD) and not fixed to the ground by adventitious roots (Table 2). Developing ramets enable quick annual extension (Figure 5, Table 2), but its short leaf live span (high SLA) results in leaf die-off during winter. High root area ratios but low root density indicate a dense fine root system focusing on quickly colonizing the soil. *M. axillaris*' exceptionally quick growth by expansion of isolated shoots and clonal growth (Figure 5, Table 2) matches its high SLA and observations of quick expansion on unstable slopes in New Zealand (Wardle 1972). The numerous adventitious roots that fix its stems to the ground (Table 2) keep the highly branched stems, with many flexible leaves (highest leaf density, high SLA) in place during high flow and provide additional soil stabilization. Its high interception volume can protect from rain splash but extends well beyond usual soil erosion flow heights (cf. Morgan, 2005). *D. octopetala*'s slow growth in 2023 matches its low SLA (Figure 2, Figure 5c). Tough, strong leaves (high LDMC) enable it to survive in highly disturbed environments, where its dense mat with prostrate, stiff, resistant, densely

clustered stems (high leaf density, SSD, stems per cm²) fixed to the ground by adventitious roots creates not only a high protection from rain splash, but also high flow resistance by not bending or moving in flow (De Baets et al., 2009). Perpendicular growth when hit by flow indicates high phenotypic plasticity (cf. McGraw and Antonovics, 1983) that enables it to adapt its architecture to geomorphic constraints. Finally, *F. gautieri* grew in a dense, round cushion with a high interception volume made up by highly clustered, stiff, dense stems (Figures 2 a, 5b) creating high flow resistance typical for grass species. *F. gautieri*'s high root density provides resistance to overturning (Freschet et al., 2020) as well as a high potential to reduce erosion by concentrated flow (De Baets et al., 2009).

4.2 Linking trait combinations to soil erosion dynamics: Identifying soil erosion plant strategies

Our experiment showed typical changes in soil erosion dynamics over time, such as a decreasing SYs over time (Figure 3 a,b) due to sediment exhaustion with associated coarsening and surface sealing (Poesen 2017). This causes highest erosion in 2024 to occur at the upper plot parts where sediment was refilled before re-starting the experiment. Likewise, typical effects of developing vegetation show over time, with increasing infiltration due to developing root systems (Figure 3d) and decreasing flow velocities and sediment yields (Figures 3 a,b,c; Figure 4) due to developing vegetation cover and developing stabilizing root systems (Morgan, 2005; Vannoppen et al., 2015), except for *L. decidua*. However, each species also showed species-specific effects on soil erosion dynamics (cf. Bochet et al. 2000) that can be explained by its trait combinations (Figures 2, 3, 4) and suggest different “soil erosion plant strategies”: intensifier, opportunist, conqueror, builder and blocker (Figure 5).

4.2.1 The intensifier (*L. decidua*)

Significantly higher SYs for *L. decidua* than for the bare plot in the second year, low infiltration and observed channel formation and erosion (Figure 3, Figure 4, Video S6) suggest that *L. decidua* acted as an “intensifier” of soil erosion (Figure 5b). This can be explained by its thick, single stems that caused lateral flow acceleration and erosion (Diehl et al., 2017; Zong and Nepf, 2010). While its high root densities suggest good erosion protection (Vannoppen et al., 2015), this was not observed in our experiment, possibly due to its comparatively large root diameters (Figure S2, Burylo et al., 2014). Little reduction in rainfall SYs in 2023 could be explained by late development of leaves and *L. decidua*’s higher plant height. With its biomass not covering the ground, it is protecting less from splash erosion and can even increase raindrop throughfall kinetic energy and thereby erosivity (Lacombe et al., 2018; Senn et al., 2020). As *L. decidua*’s stems and roots stayed intact in the second year, they continued to focus flow, increase flow velocities and promote erosion between the two stems even after die-off, increasing runoff SY by 250% (Table 3). Thus, *L. decidua*’s “intensifier” trait combinations (single stem, high root diameters), typical for (sub)alpine tree species (cf. Kutschera et al., 1997), should be avoided on eroding alpine slopes with no undergrowth present.

4.2.2 The opportunist (*C. cochleariifolia*)

Quick, but in total limited reduction in SYs, coupled with high stem flexibility, distinct below-ground expansion, winter leaf die-off and low overall investment of biomass (Figures 2a, 4, Table 3) suggest that *C. cochleariifolia* acts as an opportunist, capturing water and sediments for its own benefit with little investment and only as long as its beneficial for its survival (Figure 5b). Quick protection from rainfall erosion (40% reduction) and runoff (77%) in the first year can be explained by its quick clonal growth of above-ground biomass, providing rainfall

protection and trapping fines in and around its above-ground biomass (Figure 5a) while its extensive, high area root system prevents soil erosion (De Baets et al., 2006; Gyssels et al., 2005) and promotes infiltration (Figure 3d), e.g. by creating large numbers of preferential flow paths (Ghestem et al., 2011). Winter leaf die-off and flexible stems with many branches that minimize drag in flow (Diehl et al., 2017; Luhar and Nepf, 2011) protect *C. cochleariifolia* from biomass loss, but limit its sediment trapping ability (Burylo et al., 2012). *C. cochleariifolia* shows phenotypic plasticity in its natural habitat, with single rosettes on strongly moving debris, while dense, turf-like habits like in our experiment develop on stable substrates (Schröter et al., 1926). Thus, *C. cochleariifolia*'s "opportunistic" trait combinations (quick clonal growth, extensive fine root system, flexible stems), typical for alpine pioneer species (Kutschera et al., 1997; Schröter et al., 1926), can be effective for quickly stabilizing eroding alpine soils, but only with short-term and overall limited effects due to seasonal variation and high flexibility. Special care needs to be taken in case of high phenotypic plasticity, with a suitable growth habit achieved prior to planting e.g. by growing on stable slopes or in greenhouses.

Figure 5: Illustration of (a) key trait gradient and combinations of investigated alpine species and (b) resulting soil erosion plant strategies based on their key effects on soil erosion dynamics.

4.2.3 The conqueror (*M. axillaris*)

Very quick and effective SY reduction and sediment trapping (Figure 3, Table 3), combined with exceptionally quick expansion and high invested biomass (Figure 4, Table 2), suggest that *M. axillaris* acts as a “conqueror”, growing as fast as it can to survive and expand on moving slopes, capturing water and sediments (Figure 5b). Quick growth of creeping stems with many branches and leaves, fixed to the ground by adventitious roots (Table 2; Figure 2a, 5d) to create high flow resistance and induce sediment trapping, can explain significant reductions in flow velocities and SYs already in the first year (Fig. 3), as well as and strong upstream sediment deposition in the second year. Together with below-ground extending stems, its numerous adventitious roots create additional below-ground stabilization and promote infiltration (Figure 3). The intense geomorphic disturbance regime in its natural habitats in New Zealand (e.g. annual rainfall 4000 mm, events > 300 mm; Eichel et al. 2023) with both higher disturbance magnitudes and frequencies and short windows of opportunity for establishment (cf. Balke et al., 2014), could explain its conquering strategy. Quick clonal, partly underground growth with high biomass investment ensure both quick effect on highly active geomorphic processes, as well as surviving them. *M. axillaris* suppresses establishment for other species (Foo et al., 2011) and could become invasive, with more than 100.000 individuals reported for a few hectares on Hawaii (Tunison and Zimmer, 1992). So despite its high effectivity, it is not advisable to use similar “conqueror” species for soil erosion protection outside their natural distribution, or when facilitative effects are required.

4.2.4 The builder (*D. octopetala*)

Slow growth with strongly increasing effects on soil erosion over time, including terrace creation, suggests that *D. octopetala* acts as a “builder”, growing slowly but optimized to make

best use of active soil erosion processes for creating its own habitat (Figure 5b). Lowest initial cover of *D. octopetala* and individual die-off could explain high runoff SYs in the first year (Figure 3, Figure 5), though stiff stems already locally capture sediments and slow flow velocities (Figure 3, Figure 4c). In the second year, highest reductions in SYs (runoff 40%, rainfall 94%) can be explained by *D. octopetala*'s geomorphologically optimized architectural and mechanical trait combinations. Its biomass is in place where it matters most: its dense mat with stiff prostrate stems, tough leaves and accumulating, long-lived and slowly decomposing leaves (cf. Eichel et al. 2016, 2017) completely covers the soil, protecting it from rain splash and inducing high flow resistance by staying stiff and being fixed in place by adventitious roots (Table 2, Figure 2a). Flow velocities decrease (Figure 3c), flow energy needed for soil detachment and sediment transport is reduced (Poesen, 2018), resulting in upstream sediment deposition, local slope reduction and terrace development ((Bochet et al., 2000; Saco et al., 2007; Figure 5c). While *D. octopetala* lost its leaves during winter in our experiment, its stems remained in place and effective during times of high runoff or moisture availability (snow melt). Landform creation by *D. octopetala* has been widely observed on eroding mountain slopes, often in combination with solifluction processes (Bamberg and Major, 1968; Eichel et al., 2017), and is linked to further facilitative effects, such as nitrogen fixation and promotion of soil development (Eichel et al., 2023a). Thus, *D. octopetala*'s builder trait combination (stiff prostrate stems, dense mat, adventitious roots, phenotypic plasticity) could be highly effective not only to mitigate soil erosion but also to create landforms, e.g. as microrefugia in a warming climate (Eichel et al. 2023b) and facilitate establishment of even more strongly stabilizing later successional species (Stokes et al., 2014). However, *D. octopetala* and possible similar species need to be given sufficient time to develop a soil erosion reducing effect.

4.2.5 The blocker (*F. gautieri*)

F. gautieri's very dense, stiff stems, expanding slowly laterally in its round cushion (Figure 2a, 5b) can explain both high SYs in the first, and low SYs with high infiltration and slower flow velocities in the second year, as they create very high flow resistance and make it act like a "blocker" for flow (Figure 5b). Stiff, dense biomass, typical for clumpy, tussocky vegetation (Morgan, 2005), is known for creating a blocking effect with resulting flow acceleration and erosion lateral to patches of plants (Figure 5c; Diehl et al., 2017; Zong and Nepf, 2010); Zong and Nepf 2010), resulting in low infiltration and reduction in flow velocities (Figure 3). Cushion roundness additionally counteracts sediment trapping, further explaining low reduction in runoff SY in the first year (Burylo et al., 2012). High root densities reducing soil detachment (Vannoppen et al., 2015) could explain reduction in runoff SYs (Table 2) despite visible channel development (Figure 5). In year 2, high infiltration and decrease in flow velocities (Figure 3) occurred when the stiff, dense tussocks finally merged cover and created a large backwater effect by effectively blocking flow (Video S2), with resulting band-like sediment deposition in a small terrace. Observed strong decrease in SYs with high cover matches high effectiveness of grass species in preventing soil erosion (De Baets et al., 2006; Erktan et al., 2013; Kervroëdan et al., 2021). *F. gautieri* is a recognized foundation species that locally creates stable conditions and a favorable microclimate on scree slopes (Al Hayek et al., 2014). Overall, grass species with similar "blocker" traits (stiff, dense stems, high root density), can be very effective for reducing soil erosion, but only if planted sufficiently dense or given sufficient time to grow dense. Otherwise, they can increase soil erosion. As *F. gautieri* is not growing clonally no further response traits to slope movements, such as burial tolerance or resprouting have

been reported (Al Hayek et al., 2014), special care might be needed to establish *F. gautieri* and similar species on eroding slopes.

4.2.6 Evidence for similar biogeomorphic plant strategies across environments

While we only investigated effects of five selected alpine plant species on soil erosion dynamics, the limited amount of viable plant strategies (Díaz et al., 2016; Grime, 1977) coupled with similar findings from other eroding hillslopes (Burylo et al., 2014; De Baets et al., 2009; Kervroëdan et al., 2021) and even rivers and saltmarshes, suggests that identified trait combinations, and resulting biogeomorphic strategies, could be repeated and possibly universal across geomorphic disturbance driven ecosystems. Several other soil erosion studies also identified clear trait combinations related to soil erosion in Mediterranean environment (Burylo et al., 2014; De Baets et al., 2009; Kervroëdan et al., 2021), suggesting that similar geomorphic constraints shape similar trait combinations. We expect existence of more or less or different soil erosion plant strategies depending on the geomorphic disturbance regime but also additional constraints such as climate, e.g. cold temperatures in mountains or dry conditions in the Mediterranean region that require further trait trade-offs (cf. Corenblit et al., 2024). In our data, adaptation of soil erosion strategies to environment shows in the strong differences between the dwarf shrubs *D. octopetala* and *M. axillaris*. While *M. axillaris* deals exceptionally well with common high magnitude or frequency processes by quick growth and large biomass, *D. octopetala* grows slowly in a less geomorphologically disturbed environment, but highly optimized in its architecture to affect soil erosion. With its above-ground biomass concentrated just above the ground, it is also able to survive and possibly affect subsurface freeze-thaw movement by solifluction (Eichel et al. 2017), which would likely not be possible for *M. axillaris*' numerous underground stems.

Geomorphic disturbance-adapted biogeomorphic plant strategies similar to our soil erosion plant strategies have been described also in other geomorphologically dynamic “biogeomorphic ecosystems”. In rivers, a similar gradient in plant traits from avoidance of disturbance by flexibility to tolerance of disturbance and impact on it by high resistance to breakage and high above and below-ground biomass h (Corenblit et al., 2024; Hortobágyi et al., 2017). For saltmarshes, similar blocking effects, flow acceleration and channelization have been reported for stiff tussock plants similar to *F. gautieri*, with landscape scales effects on channel pattern creation depending on colonization speed (Bouma et al., 2009; Schwarz et al., 2018).

4.3 Implications for soil erosion reduction on alpine hillslopes

Our results thus confirm the importance of architectural and mechanic traits for erosion reduction (De Baets et al., 2009; Stokes et al., 2014), suggesting a possible key gradient in soil erosion related plant effect traits from quickly growing and flexible to dense and stout. Furthermore, our results demonstrate the role of life history traits, with clonally quickly extending *C. cochleariifolia* and slowly laterally extending *F. gautieri* creating very different soil erosion effects in the first year, which reverse in the second year (Figure 3, Figure 4). Our results furthermore suggest a high importance of adventitious roots (*D. octopetala*, *M. axillaris*, cf. Lammeranner et al., 2007), a key trait also for riparian ecosystem engineer species (Corenblit et al., 2024, 2014). Finally, our results highlight the importance of phenotypic plasticity, which can be beneficial (*D. octopetala*) or possibly unfavorable (*C. cochleariifolia*) for soil erosion. It could also be a key trait enabling species to adapt to changing environmental conditions (Corenblit et al., 2024). Yet, to our knowledge, there are no further studies on its role for soil erosion dynamics yet.

Derived knowledge on key plant traits can be well combined with more and more readily available trait data from trait databases, making it possible to identify more alpine plant species with most suitable trait combinations and resulting soil erosion strategies across mountain regions. Several identified traits linked to engineer performance and effect on soil erosion dynamics in our data are readily and frequently available in plant trait databases such as TRY (Kattge et al., 2020), e.g. the common leaf traits SLA (> 8000 species) and LDMC (> 9000 species) linked to the leaf economic spectrum, as well as stem specific density (>12000 species) and life history traits such as plant clonal growth form (> 2500 species) and lateral spread (>2500 species). In contrast, many plant architecture related traits, such as number of stems and leaves required to calculate total leaf area and number of stems per cm² (Kervroëdan et al., 2019), or root area ratios and root tensile strength to calculate root cohesion (De Baets et al., 2009; Schmidt et al., 2001), are not yet available in ecological databases but would be very valuable to include.

Our results showed that previously identified geomorphic ecosystem engineer species (*D. octopetala*, *M. axillaris*; cf. Eichel et al. 2023) were most effective in reducing soil erosion, however, for stress-tolerant, slowly growing *D. octopetala*, it took more than one growing season to develop sufficient density. This suggests that it might be beneficial to combine different soil erosion plant strategies. For example, opportunists could be used to quickly provide key initial protection (De Baets et al. 2009), until blocker and builder species, also effective in landform creation and facilitation, can take over. Combinations of soil erosion strategy types need to be considered in the light of species and trait diversity, with contrasting previous results on their role for soil erosion reduction (Berendse et al., 2015; Kervroëdan et al., 2019; Ohler et al., 2023).

5 Conclusion

Using semi-natural soil erosion experiments in the Utrecht Botanic Gardens, we investigated the effect of five alpine plant species (*Campanula cochleariifolia*, *Festuca gautieri*, *Dryas octopetala*, *Muehlenbeckia axillaris*, *Larix decidua*) with different response and effect trait combinations on soil erosion dynamics over two growing seasons.

Our results showed that:

- (1) Key plant response and effect traits comprised architectural traits, related to area, spatial distribution and density of plant organs, and biomechanical traits, with a key gradient from quickly growing flexible species to slowly growing species with stiff and dense above-ground biomass. Additional key traits with a significant role for reducing soil erosion were adventitious roots and phenotypic plasticity, enabling plants to optimize their architecture to avoid or affect soil erosion dynamics.
- (2) Each investigated plant species possesses a specific trait combination that created species-specific impacts on soil erosion dynamics and patterns, translating into five soil erosion plant strategies: “intensifier”, “opportunist”, “conqueror”, “builder” and “blocker”. While a flexible, clonally growing herbaceous “opportunist” (*C. cochleariifolia*) and an exceptionally quickly growing dwarf shrub with underground stems (*M. axillaris*) reduced soil erosion most quickly (up to 70% in the first year), more slowly growing “ecosystem engineer” species became most effective in a second growing season. With their stiff, densely clustered (*F. gautieri*) stems, or prostrate stems fixed to the ground by adventitious roots (*D. octopetala*), these “blocker” and “builder” species decreased sediment yields by up to 97% and promoted terrace

development. In contrast, our single-stemmed alpine tree species (*L. decidua*) acted as intensifier for soil erosion dynamics, even after its dieback.

- (3) To identify further alpine plant species effective for reducing soil erosion, the key response and effect traits we identified can be extracted from common plant trait databases. Using the soil erosion plant strategies we describe, identified species can be effectively combined to provide short- and long-term reduction in soil erosion and facilitate terrace development.

Thus, owing to our trait-based approach (Ohler et al., 2023; Stokes et al., 2014), our results can be transferred across mountain regions. Our results suggest that especially more geomorphic ecosystem engineer species need to be identified, which act as builder or blocker. By promoting landform development and facilitating establishment for later successional, even more effective species, they can provide a long-term solution (> decades) for slope restoration and soil protection (Stokes et al., 2014; Walker and Shiels, 2013).

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